

PARENTAL MEDIATION STRATEGIES OF TEENAGERS' SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Studies in Nigeria have shown the prevalence of social media usage among adolescents in Nigeria and this has both positive and negative effects on them, making the need for parental mediation pertinent. Most studies on parental mediation done in Nigeria adopt quantitative method of data gathering. In order to provide in-depth understanding and additional insight into parental mediation practices and strategies in the Nigerian context, the present study adopted a qualitative approach. The objective of this study is to explore the strategies parents in Lokoja use to mediate the social media usage of their teenage children. Based on the parental mediation theory, the study made use of in-depth interview method to gather responses to questions on the mediation practices adopted by 13 parents with regard to the social media usage of their teenage children. Findings revealed that to mediate the negative influences teenagers are exposed via social media usage, parents employ a combination of strategies such as counseling, restriction, monitoring and seizing of phones. The study recommends that parents continue to update their knowledge of social media in order to guide their wards more effectively and other knowledgeable close family members such as older siblings should be involved in mediation.

Keywords: Parental mediation, Strategies, Teenagers, Social media

Introduction

We live in a world saturated with digital media which is assessed by both the young and the old. In Nigeria, teenagers were known to engage in activities that encouraged communal integration, played out-door games, consulted textbooks and adults around them for school assignments. However, the internet, social media sites and video games have surpassed these (Babatunde, 2024).

While research has shown that social media is useful for adolescents in communication, entertainment and for schoolwork, there are also risks involved which some scholars see as outweighing the benefits such as social media addiction, sleep deprivation, neglect of other commitments at home and school (Mekonen, Kumasa & Amanu, 2025). Also, parents in Nigeria at times frown at the nature of content teenagers post or share on social media, perceiving them as culturally unacceptable (Emmanuel, 2025).

Following the mass failure recorded by the nationwide United Tertiary Matriculation Board examinations in Nigeria in 2024 where a 77% failure rate was recorded, one of the reasons for decline in academic performance was attributed to distraction from social media used by many teenage secondary school students (Agbana, 2024). According to Ogungbile (2025), *tiktok* has taken on the role of a second home among many teenage secondary school and higher institution students. Similarly, Ojo (2022) revealed

that social media affects the reading culture of many teenage secondary school students in Nigeria as they prefer to spend hours on social media than read their books.

Students give attention to viewing and creating skits, participating in various challenges as they trend and are promoted by influencers, while reading culture and academic interest declines. Influencers and school teachers are in competition because students believe that attention on social media is rewarded by fame and financial gratification, that academics can give. Parents who are the primary guardians of children have a crucial role to play in managing and regulating how growing children and teens use social media, hence the need for parental mediation of the social media usage of adolescents.

Although studies have established some parental mediation strategies of digital media use such as active, restrictive and technical mediation, most studies of parental mediation done in Nigeria used a quantitative method of data gathering (James & Kur 2020, Kur, Kolo, & Iorpagher, 2022, Nwosu, Okeke & Lukan, 2022) and this method is limited because it does not allow for in-depth understanding and additional insight into parental mediation practices particularly in the Nigerian cultural context, based on human experiences.

For instance, Amobi, Sunday and Obia (2020) found that in the Nigerian context, data-limiting was an additional strategy employed by parents in Lagos to regulate the social media usage of their teenage children. The present study seeks to fill a gap in literature by using a qualitative method to find out the experiences of parents in mediating the social media usage of their teenage children. The objective of this study is to explore the strategies parents in Lokoja use to mediate the social media usage of their teenage children.

Literature Review

The emergence and spread of the Internet from the early 2000s ushered in a new area of focus in parental mediation as stakeholders began to examine the influence of the digital media use (computers, social media, mobile devices, smart phones) on children and adolescents due to the fact that digital media has potentially good or bad usage (Mathias & Singh, 2023; Iheanacho et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the mediation of adolescents' technology is a pertinent topic within the context of contemporary parenting, given that cultural parenting norms today emphasize that parents bear a major responsibility in supporting their children's cognitive skills and healthy development (Dermott & Pomati, 2016).

Researchers started with the techniques already established for television use when looking at parental mediation tactics for kids' internet use. The four main parental mediation strategies are: active mediation, participatory learning, restrictive mediation, technical mediation (Livingstone & Helsper, 2008; Clark, 2011). Restrictive mediation refers to parents setting strict rules, boundaries and limitations on their children's media consumption.

In technical mediation, parental controls are used to filter, monitor, and regulate children's online media activities. Active mediation enables parents to have conversations with their children to explain or discuss their use of digital media. Participatory learning is when parents engage in activities that encourage their kids and themselves to learn how to use digital media together.

The strategy where parents add their children as friends on social media such as Facebook or view their status on WhatsApp in order to monitor what the post online is termed non-intrusive inspection (Ho, Lwin & Chen, 2019). Chen, Liu and Tang (2023) after reviewing seventeen studies on parental mediation from 2015 to 2023 summarised the parental mediation strategies in the social media era as active, restrictive and non-intrusive inspection.

In Nigeria, some studies have been done to examine parental mediation strategies of digital media usage, especially to examine the most commonly used strategy adopted by Nigerian parents. James and Kur (2020) examined parental mediation of children's risky experiences with digital media in Minna, Nigeria, focusing on four categories of risks (conduct, content, commercial, and contact risks).

The findings of their study revealed that restrictive and active mediation strategies were the dominant strategies used by parents while technical mediation and co-use strategy were rarely used. Parents reported that restrictive mediation strategy was the most successful in mediating children's risky experiences with digital media. Adigwe and van der Walt (2020) examination of parental mediation of online media activities of children in Nigeria using a parent-child approach among teenagers and their parents in Lagos also found that restrictive and active mediation were mostly used, compared to participatory learning and technical mediation.

Their study found more stronger association between parents and child reports in active and restrictive mediation. Adigwe (2024) while investigating gender perspectives of adolescents' online risk taking and parental mediation in Nigerian families outlined four mediation strategies including active, restrictive, technical and participatory learning. Mekonen et al. (2024) revealed that limiting time, selecting content and co-view were the methods parents in Ethiopia used to supervise their adolescent children.

Amobi, Sunday and Obia (2020) investigated the extent to which parents use selected mediation strategies for the mobile and social media engagement of their teenage children and the influence of those strategies on parent-child relationship, using a survey method and focus group discussion of parents and teenagers from selected secondary schools from 5 local government areas in Lagos. Their findings showed that parents mostly use instructive (active) mediation and data-limiting strategy, while digital and technical mediation technique was rarely used due to the complexity of the tools.

Most of these studies are limited because they adopted the parental mediation strategies found in previous empirical studies especially conducted in western countries, and assessed the most dominant strategy used. This study seeks to fill a gap in literature by using a qualitative method to assess the strategies used by parents in Nigeria, whereby parents can relate their experience, in order to contribute to providing better in-depth understanding of parental mediation in Nigeria's cultural context. Amobi et al.'s (2020) study revealed that data-limiting strategy was an additional strategy used by parents in Nigeria. This study seeks to find out additional strategies that may be found in another city in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the theory of parental mediation. According to the theory of parental mediation, parents mediate and mitigate the detrimental impacts of the media on their children's lives by using a variety of interpersonal communication strategies (Clark, 2011). According to Lynn Clark who advanced the theory, the theory draws from the works of developmental psychologists in the early 20th century who were concerned about how interpersonal communication guided child development, such as Bandura's social learning theory (1977) which looked at parents as role models and Russian psychologist Vygotsky (1978) who theorized that children's interaction with their parents and other important figures in their lives helped them engrain social norms.

The theory has been extended in use to study parental mediation of digital media use of children with various scholars contributing to modifying the parental mediation strategies suited to internet use (Livingstone et al., 2017). This theory is directly related to the present study which seeks to find out the strategies adopted by parents in mitigating the negative outcomes that can arise from teenagers' interaction with social media.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research approach. According to Creswell (2014), the focus of qualitative research is examining and comprehending the meaning that an individual or group of individuals assigns to a social or human situation. It involves generating meaning from the experiences and opinions of the population of study. The area of the study is Lokoja, the capital city of Kogi state, North-Central Nigeria, which has a population size of 931,000 (Macrotrends, 2025).

The population of the study are parents (father or mother) resident in Lokoja who have teenage children between the ages of 15 to 17 that use social media and live with them. The parent respondents were gotten through snowballing method. One parent referred the researchers to another parent. The researchers informed the parents of the nature of the research and their confidentiality assured.

Respondents were sent a copy of the interview guide containing details about the interview. Some of the interviews were conducted face-to-face in the homes of the respondents while telephone interview was conducted with some others. The interviews were conducted between December 2023 and January 2024. Most often, each interview lasted for 20 minutes.

Questions asked were open-ended, allowing respondents relay their experiences freely and follow-up questions were asked. A total of 13 parents were interviewed, based on Bernard (2013)'s assertion that 10 to 20 core research participants are sufficient to identify and comprehend the central problems in any study of lived experience. Researchers engaged in peer debriefing with a colleague who was not involved in the research to examine assumptions about the topic and refine the thematic analysis. Responses were recorded, transcribed and thematically analysed. After data familiarisation, codes and themes were generated.

Data presentation

S/N	Informant	Code Name	Age	Gender	Occupation	Area
1	Informant 1	Inf. P1	50	Female	Civil servant	Army signal
2	Informant 2	Inf. P2	40	Female	Trader	Lokongoma
3	Informant 3	Inf. P3	51	Male	Station Manager	Mt. Patti
4	Informant 4	Inf. P4	64	Male	Retired Civil Servant	Phase 2
5	Informant 5	Inf. P5	40	Female	News Presenter	Lokongoma
6	Informant 6	Inf. P6	50	Male	Public servant	Kwarararafa
7	Informant 7	Inf. P7	67	Male	Retired Civil Servant	Phase 2
8	Informant 8	Inf. P8	40	Female	Tailor	Lokongoma
9	Informant 9	Inf. P9	37	Female	Lecturer	Felele
10	Informant 10	Inf. P10	38	Female	House wife	Zango
11	Informant 11	Inf. P11	53	Male	Engineer	Ganaja village
12	Informant 12	Inf. P12	42	Female	Business woman	Zango
13	Informant 13	Inf. P13	56	Female	Civil servant	Harmony schl

Thematic Analysis

Theme 1: Parental Mediation Strategies

The strategies, interactions or ways through which parents' guide their teenage children in their usage of social media to minimise negative effect that could arise from usage and maximise opportunities is known as parental mediation strategies. The data in this study shows that parental mediation strategies are used by parents to guide their teenage children in their navigation through social media. Parents explained the mediation strategies they employed in the following subthemes.

Subtheme 1: Seizing of Phones

Some parents have maintained that another strategy they use to ensure compliance is seizing of the phones from their teenagers when they refuse to adhere to the instruction by parents and when they observe that they spend too much time on social media. Seizing the phone implies parents taking the personal phones of their teenage children away from them and not allowing them access it for a period of days or weeks.

This was corroborated by the teenagers who mentioned that their parents seized their phones at times when they felt they were spending too much time on social media, much to their dismay. In the words of Inf. P4, *"I seize his phone when I notice high usage"*. Meanwhile, Inf. 3 recounted thus: *There was a time I discovered my daughter was on the phone for several hours, and I seized the phone for some days and educated her about addiction. I encouraged her to discipline herself in the amount of time she spends doing this or that on the phone. She appreciated my counsel, and she came back to tell me that for some days she had not gone online*(Inf. P3).

In the words of Inf. P7, he said: *If I call my son more than once and I see he is distracted by what he is doing online, I seize his phone and give him back the next day and other times, several days after.* This view was shared by Inf P2. Their response shows that at times, one thing that upsets parents when teenagers are online with their phones is when they call them for something but they are distracted by their phones.

Subtheme 2: Restrictive mediation

From the data collected from parents in this study, parents limit the amount of time their teenagers can use on the social media in order to minimize the possibility that their teenagers will be addicted to social media or exposed to unwanted and unsolicited information. Some of the parents in this study shared their views on how they use the restrictive mediation strategy to guide their children usage of social media, especially to guard against spending too much time on the gadgets while abandoning other offline activities like studies and house chores, being on social media at odd times.

Few of them also limit the number of social media platforms their teenage children engage in. For instance, Inf. P7 shared how he placed restriction on the time of day his teenage children access social media. He said; *I regulate the time of usage, especially at night, when all sorts of unnecessary conversations can take place. Therefore, I will always collect the phone and keep it with me till morning.*

Also, Inf. P6 who is a public servant stated that *One of the strategies I use is agree on an acceptable time to be online by them.* On enquiry on the amount of time perceived to be acceptable, Inf. P6 said *The most acceptable time to allow my kids to be online is between 7 to 9pm daily but on weekends, it could be longer if they are done with their assignments and house chores and on Sundays, 5 to 9pm. 4 hours and above by kids online without any official assignment or any pre-advertised and approved targeted program is considered too much a time for a teen to be online*(Inf. P6).

This view was shared by Inf. P4. In addition, Inf. P4 said *I withdraw the phones completely during exams. In the words of Inf. P1, she shared that: I always tell her that there's a limit to the usage of phones. When it's time to read, I tell her to drop the phone and go and read because you cannot use a phone in the exam hall. It's what you read you will write down. When she doesn't listen, I collect the phone. When it's 10 p.m., she must go to bed. I also don't buy her data because I don't want her to use the phone* (Inf. P1).

On his part, Inf. P3 noted that, *I manage the time my children spend on social media. I cannot allow them to be on their phone all the time as if the phone is their life. Sometimes they can be on Whatsapp, Facebook or whatever and then even their domestic chores will be abandoned. So I always guide them and say this is the time for this and that* (Inf. P3).

Some parents (Inf. P1, Inf. P6) mentioned that one way they restrict their teenage children's access to social media is limiting their access to data. According to Inf. P2 who is a trader, *'I also don't buy her data because I don't want her to use the phone'*.

Another means of restriction is by limiting the number of social media platforms teenage children engage in. For example, Inf. P12 said *I only allow my child to use Whatsapp and no Facebook. In the words of one of the parent Inf. P12 while recounting an experience with her son, 'There was a time he posted himself on one scary mask, one of those snapchat filter and I saw it and asked him to remove it immediately.it looked scary. People might read different meaning to it and I am just trying to protect his image. I also don't expect my son to post his achievement on social media'*. (Inf. P12). This shows that parents also restrict the content their teenage children post online.

Subtheme 3: Monitoring Social Media Usage

Some parents (Inf. P2, Inf. P7, Inf. P10, Inf. P5) expressed that they monitor the activities of their children on social media by adding them as friends to keep an eye on what they post online. Inf. P10 while stressing the need for monitoring, lamented on the role of parents and secondary schools in promoting the use of phones by teenagers in secondary schools, which in her view is too early for them. *For me, parents should exercise patience before handing them phones. Because once you give them phones, they can burst into anywhere they like on social media. When there is no one to caution them they will continue. Even if parents give those children phone, they should do their best to monitor them. Although I know you can't fully monitor somebody* (Inf. P10).

Following the position of Inf. P10, Inf. P1 emphasised the need for parents to desist from handing phones to their children at early age which they can use to operate social media accounts. She said *'Parents should try to check what their children do on their phones. Before you give them the phone, they should not be less than 15 or 16 years or in SS3. Not that children will be in JSS 2 and you will be giving them phone'* (Inf. P1).

Parents also check the phones of their teenage children from time to time. In the words of Inf. P2, *'Her father also monitors what she does. There was a time he saw that she opened another account on Facebook. He called her, sat her down and made sure she deleted the account. We make sure she uses one account, her cousins and family members have her as friends so we can see what she does. We don't tolerate her using strange names that no one will know about. There was also a time her dad called her after church service. He caught her online in church and cautioned her. Why should you be in church and be on social media. Is the phone running away?'* (Inf. P2).

Parents' monitoring their teenagers on social media is a delicate balance between ensuring their safety and respecting their privacy. Some parents monitor their teen's activities without their knowledge. Inf. P7stated that: *I will monitor what they are saying, although most of them tend to lock up their phones.*

So, if they drop it, you may not be able to access it to go through what they are doing, but at the same time, because we constantly warn them about the dangers, in most cases they avoid such things (Inf. P7).

On the contrary, Inf. P11 stated; *"I bump into their supposed privacy, collect and ransack phones because 'I'm Daddy'. I ask to have a view of what they do occasionally"*. In the same vein, Inf. P10 said *'I also check her Whatsapp when she posts on her status. She doesn't post too much. Mostly what she puts on social media is all these cartoon pictures'* (Inf. P10).

Similarly, Inf. P5, Inf. P6 stressed the need for vigilance in monitoring. In the words of Inf. P5, *The most effective approach to safeguarding your children from the potential pitfalls of social media is through vigilant monitoring. Recognizing that they may lack certain insights, it becomes essential to guide them along the right path. This is why I advocate for monitoring as a proactive and effective strategy* (Inf. P5). Inf. P2 emphasised the need for parents not to think their teenage children have outgrown monitoring because teenagers face peer pressure that could be detrimental to them.

Subtheme 4: Giving Counsel

While identifying counselling as a way to checkmate the activities on teenagers on social media, some of the informants shared their opinion. Counselling in this study involves parents encouraging proper use, giving counsel and caution from engaging in inappropriate usage or activities of their teenage children on social media. Inf. P12 simply said *"I make time to talk to them about the risk that is involved"*. Inf. P6 noted thus: *I do have engagement with my kids on the negative influences on social media and let them know the dangers associated with the web, the good aspect, the bad one too and need to be conscious every time and not succumb to peer pressures, as many have gone astray from wrong use of social media, I do show them examples too* (Inf. P6).

On his part, 67-year-old Retired Civil Servant, Inf. P7 explained why talking to teens is more advantageous. He stated thus: *You can't beat some of the children because of their ages. So, parents should be able to talk to them. All you can do is to give them advice that will help them realize that they should slow down on what they are doing. The kids should also be cautious and take time to listening to their parents and not wait for their father to come around to yell and create noise. Instead, they should do it on their own. They should also exercise caution and utilize their senses, as they are aware of the dangers in using social media and should avoid sin and anything that could cause them trouble* (Inf. P7).

Inf. P10 explained that she encourages her daughter to verify news before sharing and cautions from spreading fake news. *'Yes. I do caution my daughter. Sometimes I lecture her about what to do and what not to do on social media. For example, I tell her that it is not everything she sees that she shares. Some people fabricate things and post them on social media and some will not verify whether it is true or not. So I caution her on such things that she should not help people spread fake news. Something you are not aware of and don't know when it happened, please stay out of it. I tell her that.'*

Also, Inf. P1 opined that she and her husband gave their daughter specific instruction on how to guide against contact risk on social media before she opened her social media account. She stated thus: *We sat her down and really talked to her. We made her understand that it is not everybody who sends a friend request that you should grant, and it is not every message sent to you that you should reply to. The reason we bought the phone for her was mainly for academics and to be able to communicate with her while she's in school* (Inf. P1).

On her part, Inf. P8 shared that: *Like me, if my children carry their phone too much, I will tell them to go and drop it and read their book so that Facebook will not just collect their brain. At least if you enter class and your aunty say 1+1 and they now say Facebook, you know that one is not good. I dey always warn my children against involving in yahoo yahoo. All those bad bad things, I don't like it. Those people*

wey go dey post nakedness, I don't support. So I cannot say don't enter Facebook because even me, I dey use Facebook but I will make sure I warn them on what is not good(Inf. P8).

In addition to, some of the informants emphasized the importance of parents making their teens understand online risks as the first step to guarding the behaviour of teens online. This is the reason why Inf. P3 opined that:*Monitoring is not going to help if the children themselves do not understand the benefit or implication. So, what I do mostly is tell them the dangers or areas they should not go. Don't go to sites where you will be watching pornography or other activities that are of no benefit to you. Anything you want to do should be evaluated. I ask my children, 'If I tell you this thing is not good, you stop doing it because I say it is not good or because you understand that it is not good'? So, I want them to understand why something is not good so that they don't just pretend to accept it and then engage in it when I'm not around. I also caution them that something is not right just because everyone is doing it. So, when you know the right thing, no one will force you to do the wrong thing* (Inf. P3).

However, Inf. P3, Inf. P7 and Inf. P8 stressed that in counselling, parents should adopt a friendly approach and make out time for their teenage children. For instance, Inf. P8 said: *Parents should calm down for their children at times. Not to shout always. Let your children see you as their own friend. If you can be close with your children, it will be hard for them to make mistake. Because they can call your attention to somethings and you will correct them. Not that you yell at any little thing. Some parents also don't have time for their children which is not good*(Inf. P8).

While 39 years old Inf. P9 simply said “*Make friends with your teenage children. That way, they can get along easily and they can open up freely*”. Furthermore, few of the parent respondents add that aside from talking to their children about the risks online, they encourage them to find ways to maximize the benefits. Inf.P3 stated that *‘I asked one of my daughters that ‘how much money has come to your pocket from what you have been doing on social media’? she said ‘daddy, nothing. But I’m enjoying it’. I said don’t enjoy what is not giving you any return. I tell her she is patronising someone’s business, the moment you recharge you are paying to someone’s account. Now as you’re doing that what are you selling that can come back to you? Begin to think of that so that you can use the social media for your own benefits, not just to benefit another person while you are whiling away time unnecessarily’*. (Inf. P3)

From another angle, some of the parents use their religious inclination to guide and counsel their wards on how to use social media appropriately (Inf. P10, Inf. P4, Inf. P13). Inf. P4 stated that *‘I have interactions with my son, I let him know that there is need to allow the Holy Spirit guard his heart so he can avoid sites that are not good for him. I always tell him God is not in support of such things and I pray for him* (Inf. P4).

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed the strategies parents employed in mediating social media use by their teenage children which includes; restrictive mediation, monitoring, counselling and seizing of phones. In contrast, James and Kur (2020)’s study of parents in Minna, Nigeria noted four mediation strategies used by them including restrictive, active, technical and co-use mediation strategies, even though restrictive and active were the most dominant.

Findings from the present study shows that most parents combine active, restrictive mediation and monitoring. They give instructions and a lot of warnings on how and when teenagers should use social media, ensuring they stop their teenagers from using social media at certain times. Also, parents who use social media additionally monitor the activities of their teenagers by viewing their status on *WhatsApp* or adding them as friends on Facebook, and instructing them (their teenage children) at times to take down posts they are not comfortable with. Parents in the study advocated for a friendly approach to be used in

giving counsel to their wards, rather than non-friendly approaches like yelling at them, to encourage compliance.

Parents giving instructions, warnings and counsel to their wards which was termed counselling in the study is likened to instructive technique (Amobi et al., 2020). However, an additional feature of counselling strategy in this study is that parents at times involve their religious inclination in counselling. The active, restrictive and non-intrusive inspection strategies found in this study are in line with Chen, Liu and Tang (2023) that these three strategies are the major parental mediation strategies in the social media era.

However, this study found an additional strategy in the Nigerian context which is the practice of parents seize or take away the phones of their teenage children when they notice them spending too much time on it, and when they do not comply to rules, as a way of guiding against social media addiction. This is an addition to the strategy of data-limiting listed by Amobi et al. (2020) which was applied by parents in Lagos Nigeria.

This finding of this study shows that parents also limit the data they provide for their teens as a means of restricting their frequency of access to social media and this is in consonance with Amobi et al. (2020). An additional feature of restrictive mediation found to be used by parents in this study is restricting the social media platforms their teenage children engage in. This is in line with Mekonen et al. (2024) which found that parents prevented their children from using platforms they believed were inappropriate for them.

This study found that technical mediation which involves the use of filters and software to block the access of children to apps that parents do not want them to access was rarely used strategy. This finding is in line with Amobi et al. (2020) that parents used instructive and data-limiting strategies more than technical or digital strategies. However, combining strategies is consistent with Barkin et al. in Chen et al. (2023) that 59% of parents utilise numerous mediation tactics at the same time and this has effect on the kind of online risk teenagers are exposed to.

The findings of this study are in line with the proposition of the parental mediation theory that parental intervention mediates the negative effects the media, in this case, digital media, could have on teenagers. One of the criticisms of the theory was that there are gaps on how applicable the theory is to other types of media that have developed after television such as the internet.

This led to the theory been expanded to digital media usage with many scholars putting forward parental mediation strategies of social media usage. The current study contributes by revealing more strategies adopted by parents in Nigeria, such as seizing of mobile devices, adding to the body of knowledge of parental mediation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The media has become an integral part of the everyday life of both the young and old and it has the capacity to shape the minds of young adults positively and negatively. Therefore, it pertinent for youngsters to be guided by parents, who are the closest to them in terms of physical proximity, on how they engage with social media platforms and make sense of social media messages.

The study showed that parents apply a combination of strategies in mediating the usage of social media platforms (especially *Facebook* and *WhatsApp*) by their teenage children such as counselling, restriction, monitoring and seizing of mobile devices, providing better understanding of the parental mediation practices in the study area. This study has provided an additional strategy used by parents in the study area, which is seizing of mobile devices as a means of ensuring compliance, thereby contributing to the body of knowledge on parental mediation strategies.

The study recommends that parents should apply a friendly approach in mediation. Parents also need to update themselves on social media usage, as it keeps evolving, in order to equip themselves with adequate knowledge for better guidance, because most times, they are not as social media savvy as youngsters.

Other family members such as older siblings who are more knowledgeable should also be involved in providing guidance to adolescents. Schools need to be involved in mediation, educating teenagers on the positives and negatives of social media usage. Future studies can assess the perspectives of teenagers on the various mediation strategies adopted by their parents, with a view of determining their effectiveness.

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